

User perspectives in the Design of Interactive Everyday Objects for Sustainable Behaviour

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Abstract

Addressing efficient management of energy has become a central objective due to the scarcity of traditional energy sources and global warming. To cope with this overarching issue, some technological solutions such as Smart Grids, Internet of Things or Demand response are proposed. However, the majority of them overlooks the role of human beings in the equation. Moreover, the very nascent body of research combining human and machine intelligence proposes methods, frameworks, and guidelines which vary depending on the application scenario complicating the selection of gold-standards to ensure seamless cooperation between smart devices and people. Hence, the purpose of this paper is to provide a set of design-hypotheses to devise augmented objects that ally with their users to reduce energy consumption. We expect designers, engineers, makers or even hobbyists in the intersection between technology-enablers (through IoT) and behavioural scientists to benefit from them. To this aim, we describe the results of a long-term study in office-based workplaces, where participants were randomly assigned to different experimental conditions (persuasion, dashboard, and automation) to increase their energy-efficient behaviour. Grounded Theory analysis was applied over qualitative data collected during focus group sessions obtaining five themes around a central category. The resulting themes were linked to design-hypotheses for IoT devices which were then tested through the implementation of a new IoT object also conceived for the workplace.

Keywords: Internet of Things, Persuasive Technology, Grounded Theory, Human Computer Interaction, Design for Sustainable Behaviour Change

1. Introduction

In recent years, the Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and Persuasive Technology communities started to increase their attention to sustainability issues because environmental preservation is strongly dependent on human behaviour. In this field, a large body of previous research from the early XXI century has evidenced the value of persuasive feedback to foster behaviour change [1] [2] [3]. Persuasion for sustainability has its roots in the application of Fogg’s framework [4] for ”computers as persuaders” to the topic of pro-environmental sustainability. Taking the existing context into account, this paper focuses on a single but widespread environmental issue, which is to reduce the energy footprint at the workplace, changing the way employees use private and shared electronic devices by augmenting them with IoT technologies. This interest is supported by scientific evidence, according to Brynjarsdttir et al. [5] who found that more than half of the papers they reviewed in their analysis of persuasive technologies tackled energy-related topics. In the same vein, Di Salvo et al [6] reviewed the body of knowledge on Sustainable HCI finding different genres overall focused on ambient awareness, persuasive technology and sustainable interaction design. Similarly, Pierce and Paulos [2] stated that energy consumption was the primary focus on sustainable HCI works after reviewing 51 papers on the field. More relevant to our research was to understand that the analysis carried out on this topic revealed that there is a growing interest in augmenting legacy or new everyday devices with persuasive technology to help people to form eco-minded behaviours. In Figure 1 different augmented objects devised to bring awareness about energy consumption through eco-feedback (i.e. a term coined by Froehlich [7] which provides the idea of informing users and make them reflect over resource waste through ambient feedback) can be observed [1] [8] [9] [10] [11] [12] [13] [3] [14] [15].

Figure 1: Persuasive IoT objects found in the literature which were designed for promoting sustainable behaviour change through tangible or ambient interaction.

29 Despite this growing interest on smart devices and persuasion for enhanc-
 30 ing pro-environmental behaviour, the variety of possible sustainable actions,
 31 the desire or undesired willingness to make them, and the diversity of users
 32 (profiles, traits, interests, beliefs, etc.) make hard to find in the existing liter-
 33 ature a set of comprehensive guidelines tailored for the specific purpose that
 34 the designer desires. Furthermore, scholars on Sustainable HCI field raised
 35 their concern about the feasibility of persuasion to maintain the target behav-
 36 iour throughout the time [16, 17]. A more recent review of the literature
 37 did also not found enough evidence to support the hypothesis that feedback
 38 through digital technology leads to lasting behaviour change (whereas, it
 39 found after reviewing 72 studies that feedback through digital technology
 40 has the potential to disrupt undesired habits) [18]. In conclusion, with ex-
 41 ceptions, the majority of the studies do not last more than one month and,
 42 therefore, is still difficult to evaluate the real impact of ICT-based persuasion
 43 on behaviour change throughout the time.

44 Taking these open issues into account, this piece of research seeks to
 45 offer an ensemble of design-hypotheses that researchers on the area of sus-

46 tainability, and specifically in energy awareness through IoT, might follow
47 when approaching the design of persuasive systems. With this purpose, we
48 conducted an empirical intervention instrumenting with sensing technology
49 several capsule-based coffee machines in different work environments for more
50 than one year. Three experimental conditions were evaluated which entailed
51 leveraging various features on the appliances: (i) persuasive feedback; (ii) en-
52 ergy monitoring through a dashboard; and (iii) automated operation to avoid
53 forgetfulness. After analysing the quantitative and qualitative data gathered
54 from experiments and focus groups with the participants of the study, we are
55 able to provide cues on how to transform the design recommendations into
56 a real IoT device also conceived for office-based workplaces.

57 **2. Related Work**

58 The selection criteria of the body of research reviewed was based on the
59 idea that the targeted works should have presented a physical object aiming
60 to promote sustainable behaviour change either by using aesthetics, ambient
61 feedback, or tangible interaction. Besides, the works should have explicitly
62 stated that their approaches contribute to the Internet of Things, Ubiqui-
63 tous computing (UbiComp) or Pervasive computing fields. Furthermore, the
64 studies where the physical interactive objects were conceived for the work en-
65 vironment were preferred over those more oriented to private settings. How-
66 ever, in some cases, these were complemented with devices designed for other
67 use contexts.

68 Power-aware Cord is an electrical power-strip in which the cord was aug-
69 mented to expose the electricity being consumed in real-time through ambient
70 light. The bigger the energy drawn by the power-strip plug, the brighter the
71 cord is [1]. In this work, the light is used emotionally and qualitatively, aim-
72 ing at symbolising the energy in a more understandable way than the abstract
73 information that offers the raw energy data (e.g. kWh). Very similar to the
74 Power-aware cord, Quintal et al. [19] devised a common two spots type F wall
75 socket redesigned with two main goals: to process consumption data by using
76 a microcontroller and to provide the capability to display just-in-time visual
77 information (through the ambient LED's built-in on the socket that changed
78 from green to red by comparing the real-time consumption with a baseline
79 for the device it is connected to). Waterbot is another device that provides
80 ambient feedback about water usage in a kitchen's sink through visual and
81 auditory reminders [8]. While using ambient light to offer visual reminders,

82 it also uses the sound as an eco-feedback technique to motivate the water
83 saving. Similarly, 'Show-me' displays the amount of water that is being used
84 during the shower through an LED strip assembled to the shower's stick [9].
85 These three ambient displays apply ambient light to visualise the impact of
86 some common misbehaviour in the use of basic resources such as electricity
87 and water metaphorically.

88 Stropky Kettle is an augmented appliance that aimed to break the user's
89 kettle overflow behaviour applying barriers to goal-attainment and punish-
90 ment. This approach is based on the idea that rational information is not
91 enough to change the desired behaviour. The barrier is applied to only who
92 performs the negative behaviour [10]. Besides, the punishment as a behaviour
93 change strategy is also remarkable through the creation of a barrier to habit
94 execution.

95 Watt-lite [11] and Energy-Aware clock [12] are two works that aim to
96 explore tangible data and non-obtrusive interaction to reduce energy con-
97 sumption. Both works implement displays through playful interactions and
98 visualisations to engage the users and let them explore the energy-related
99 data to improve the understanding of the energy. Although these works do
100 not address behaviour change as a principal objective, they are intended to
101 reach the awareness and the motivation of the individuals in a social context
102 (e.g. families or workplaces). Social-coffee maker [13] applies social norm
103 strategies to improve the awareness of employees in shared spaces, increasing
104 the motivation through the influence of the group and peer pressure. The
105 coffee maker published tweets whenever someone left it switched on after
106 preparing a coffee as well as it tweeted its daily energy consumption in order
107 to be tracked by its followers on the Social Network. Thieme et al. [3]
108 devised BinCam, a social persuasive rubbish-bin with a built-in camera to
109 motivate tenants to adopt recycling habits and reduce food waste. This work
110 also applies social influence to foster awareness through behaviour change.
111 Besides, it uses a Social Media network to provide social pressure, punishing
112 the individuals who performed the adverse action through the publication
113 of their bad habit in the site. Interactive living plants were designed by
114 Holstius et al. [14]. The authors created a robotic analog of a plant that
115 mimics photo-tropic behaviour, combining living organisms and technology.
116 These plants were used to display information as they do in their natural
117 context, implementing emotional and qualitative information in the inter-
118 face and improving the impact of the display in the individual's awareness
119 through intuitive and organic interactions and visualisations. Also using tan-

120 gible interactions through shaping memory alloys, Laschke et al.[15] created
121 The Never Hungry Caterpillar, a device aimed at avoiding energy waste from
122 keeping TVs, screens and similar electronics products in standby mode un-
123 consciously. The Caterpillar is a power socket that mimics a living animal
124 that is connected to the device. When using the devices typically, it moves
125 smoothly, as if it was breathing. However, whenever the device is put in
126 standby mode, the device starts to twist in awkward ways as if it was on
127 pain and the only way of overcoming that "pain" is by switching the device
128 off completely.

129 There are also some products commercially available in this area. Watt-
130 son¹ from DIY Kyoto shows the overall electricity use in numbers and colours.
131 This energy monitor captures real-time information of the energy consump-
132 tion displaying it in different metrics, both quantitative (kWh and economic
133 value) and qualitative (glows in colours depending on the quantity of electric-
134 ity used). Another product that can be found in the market is the Ambient
135 Orb². It is a frosted-glass ball that illuminates a varying degree of colours to
136 represent critical peak demand conditions on the smart grid. Finally, the Nest
137 Thermostat³ is an intelligent device that aims to learn the user's heating and
138 cooling habits to help optimise scheduling and power usage. The machines
139 reward the users with a Leaf if they set up the temperature according to the
140 Nest recommendations to save energy. Although the temperature can be set
141 by automated processes, the rewards offer a motivational approach addressed
142 to the user, aiming at improving the desired behaviour and motivating the
143 user to maintain the sustainable habit.

144 The majority of the works reviewed devised everyday things taking into
145 account the emotional bond that final users may create with the object or
146 the objective that these pursue. Besides, the behavioural approach is mainly
147 focused on the improvement of the ease of use, being the barriers and obtru-
148 siveness significantly less applied (e.g. stropky kettle). Furthermore, existing
149 research mainly targets individual awareness rather than groups. It promotes
150 an easy and intuitive positive use of smart objects to facilitate the interaction
151 to adopt or maintain the targeted behaviour. Besides, there is a unanimity
152 of works that decided to apply the central or direct route of persuasion for

¹<http://www.diykyoto.com/>

²<http://www.ambientdevices.com/about/consumer-devices>

³<https://nest.com/thermostats/nest-learning-thermostat/overview/>

153 providing nudges instead of the peripheral one [20]. It means that the body
154 of research aims at making people reflect on their actions rather than nudg-
155 ing them to do actions subtly (e.g. using emotions as triggers or subliminal
156 priming). Finally, most of the works were only tested during short periods
157 with exceptions on the context of the household. Sustainable HCI field de-
158 mands more long term results to examine ICT-based persuasion results over
159 longer periods as some voices raised their concern about the feasibility of
160 persuasion to maintain the target behaviour throughout the time [16, 17].

161 **3. Long-term Study**

162 We carried out an experimental intervention of one year designed to test
163 the effectiveness of persuasive techniques to raise energy efficiency awareness
164 in the mid and long-term in office environments. To this aim, we designed
165 a between-group field study related to the use of electrical coffee machines
166 separated into two phases: baseline creation and piloting. In the former
167 stage, we calculated the energy consumption baseline of the coffee maker.
168 In the latter stage, we continued monitoring energy consumption. Still, we
169 introduced three different experimental conditions linked to the appliances
170 to cope with energy inefficiency: Persuasion, Web-based dashboards, and
171 automation.

172 *3.1. Initial Setup and Baseline Creation*

173 In general terms, we embedded energy measurement equipment within
174 the electrical capsule-based coffee machines of fifteen different workplaces
175 distributed between two big cities of Spain (Madrid, Bilbao). Specifically,
176 the tracking and monitoring of energy were done by embedding in each coffee
177 maker an Ethernet-based Arduino board with an energy meter that was able
178 to send the consumption data to an own remote server [21] (see Figure 3.1).

The energy consumption data flow from the Arduino microcontroller to the remote server where the data was stored for future processing and analysis.

179 The reasons why we selected coffee machines for the field study were: 1)
 180 they are pretty common in work environments and are an element of shared
 181 use; 2) they consume large amounts of energy compared to other work appli-
 182 ances such as monitors or laptops (A report on appliances' consumption holds
 183 that some models of coffee machines can exceed the electricity consumption
 184 of A-class ovens or A++ refrigerators along the year because of continuous
 185 pump pressure maintaining and water heating [22]). More than one hundred
 186 people were recruited from the different fifteen work-offices that participated
 187 in the long-term study. They were all recruited following a snowball proce-
 188 dure, and their participation was voluntary (we raffled an energy monitoring
 189 system among participants who completed the whole study).

190 During the initial set-up of the experiment to calculate the energy base-
 191 line, five out of the recruited fifteen groups dropped out the long-term study
 192 before its completion⁴. Having evaluated the impact of this dropout rate on
 193 the validity of the experimental results according to [23], we decided to carry
 194 on with the remaining ten groups (N = 90) which are described in Table 1.

195 In order to help with the understanding of the different participants'
 196 profiles, in Appendix A we describe the groups and some of their main char-
 197 acteristics.

⁴The main reasons for attrition during this experimental phase were: 1) some groups changed or ended their business activity during the piloting; 2) other groups changed from capsule-based coffee maker to filter-based appliances being the researchers unable to track individual usage of the coffee machines; finally 3) whereas we raffled an energy monitoring system some work-groups decided voluntarily to not follow up with the experiment - recall that no pecuniary rewards were given.

Table 1: The column's name refer to: name of the groups that participated in the study, the city (BIO - Bilbao or MAD - Madrid), the treatment they were assigned to, the type of work which is performed within these groups, the number of users of the coffee-maker in each space and the average age of them.

	Treatment assigned	Type of workplace	Participants & Average age
Bailen (BIO)	Persuasion	Coworking	8 (33)
Comunica (BIO)	Automation	Administrative services	8 (35)
Computing (BIO)	Dashboard	Tech. Research group	4 (28)
IEEC (MAD)	Dashboard	Tech. Research group	4 (42)
Life (BIO)	Automation	Tech. Research group	12 (28)
Mobility (BIO)	Persuasion	Tech. Research group	15 (28)
MORElab (BIO)	Automation	Tech. Research group	9 (28)
ServGen (BIO)	Dashboard	Administrative services	3 (43)
Techabout (BIO)	Persuasion	Tech-based SME	4 (33)
Tecnologica (MAD)	Persuasion	Tech-based SME	23 (38)
TOTAL			90

198 *3.2. Between-groups Intervention*

199 As have been observed in Table 1, the random assignment of the experi-
200 mental conditions among the ten workplaces remained as follows: 1) *Persua-*
201 *sive feedback (4 workplaces)*: a combination of real-time ambient feedback
202 and subtle visual hints to support the user’s decision-making about when to
203 switch off the appliance; 2) *Energy-dashboard (3 workplaces)*: participants
204 were provided with a Web site to track their energy consumption associ-
205 ated to the appliance (i.e. self-monitoring and rational information through
206 comparisons with historical energy data); and 3) *Automation (3 workplaces)*:
207 coffee makers were modified to autonomously switch the appliances off when-
208 ever they were not in use (i.e. the rationale behind automation was providing
209 a sense of comfort to the users relieving them from the task of switching the
210 appliance on and off). The three experimental conditions are depicted in
211 Figure 2. As the persuasion condition holds the hypothesis of this study, it
212 has been represented in Figure 3 for a better understanding of its operation.

Figure 2: The three different experimental treatments that were randomly assigned to the participating groups.

Figure 3: The persuasive coffee makers provided just-in-time visual cues to help users in energy efficiency decision-making. On the first image, a user approaches its finger to switch off the device. In the second and third pictures, the augmented appliance detects the motion close to the button and informs the user to not switch it off by activating a built-in visual alert. As can be observed in the first picture of Figure 2, the subtle message to prevent the operation of the appliance is "Please, leave me on".

213 It is important to emphasise that both persuasive feedback and automa-
 214 tion rely on an underlying ARIMA model, which is a statistical method for
 215 time series forecasting. Thus, the smart coffee makers were able to predict
 216 the number of users that were about to use the coffee maker in 1-hour slots
 217 during the day [24]. With this information, in the persuasive condition, the
 218 appliance suggested users operate the on-off button (e.g. Figure 3), while
 219 in the automation condition, the appliance switches on or off deliberately
 220 without human intervention to minimise the energy waste.

221 3.3. Quantitative Results

222 At the end of the study, it was demonstrated quantitatively that the
 223 IoT-based Persuasive treatment helped to save most energy than the other
 224 two treatments [25]. Specifically, we found that the IoT-based Persuasive
 225 treatment helped to save most energy than the other two treatments reducing
 226 the energy waste by 44.53%. The Automation treatment also helped to
 227 reduce energy waste by 14.19%. Finally, the Dashboard approach did not
 228 lead to a reduction of energy waste remaining with a similar percentage as
 229 the beginning of the experiment. For the sake of better understanding, we
 230 refer to "save energy" to the fact that the coffee makers diminished the
 231 quantity of wasted energy due to the generalised abuse of standby mode on
 232 these appliances (i.e. substantially reducing the time that a coffee machine

233 is switched on but is not preparing coffee). This amount of energy is not
234 negligible since the coffee makers are periodically maintaining the pressure
235 pump ready to be used or heating the water for the next coffee cup.

236 Because of this finding, we wanted to grasp detailed qualitative informa-
237 tion from users to understand the causes of the persuasive intervention being
238 more effective than automation or dashboard.

239 *3.4. Qualitative Analysis*

240 While science has a strong reliance on quantitative and experimental
241 methods, there are many complex, socially-based phenomena in HCI that
242 cannot be easily quantified or experimentally manipulated. Within HCI,
243 there is the recognition that the focus on tasks is not enough to design and
244 implement an effective system. Therefore, identifying users' emotional and
245 social drives and perspectives; their motivations, expectations, trust, iden-
246 tity, social norms, and so on are paramount for creating more than 'just
247 appealing' designs [26]. Hence, at the end of the between-group study (i.e.
248 when the experimental conditions were removed from all workplaces), we
249 ran several focus group sessions with participants who volunteered to join
250 the dynamics from each of the study-groups of Table 1 according to Merton
251 et al.'s. guidelines [27]. We managed to have —at least— one representative
252 from each of the ten remaining groups. Audio data from each session were
253 recorded and manually transcribed for further analysis through Grounded
254 Theory (GT) [28]. In the following, we describe what GT is and how we ap-
255 plied this methodology to the data obtained from groups who interacted with
256 the coffee-makers augmented with IoT-based persuasive systems to extract
257 design-insights that help to inform the design for similar everyday intelligent
258 devices created in the future. Following the specifications exposed by Heckler
259 [29] about the epistemic status of design guidelines, and due to the limited
260 amount of empirical data, in this work, the guidelines derived from the study
261 will be named as "design hypotheses", which will need further validation.

262 *3.4.1. Grounded Theory-based Approach*

263 According to Charmaz [30], GT is an established method for studying
264 qualitative information where codes are generated from the data rather than
265 relying on pre-existing categories. Thus, it can be considered as an inductive
266 method. It includes Open, Axial, and Selective Coding as phases to generate
267 a new theory, as can be observed in Figure 4. We applied this methodology
268 to analyse the qualitative data extracted from the focus group sessions to

269 produce design insights for creating augmented persuasive IoT devices that
270 promote energy efficiency practices taking into account the social phenomena
271 of the workplace context.

272 There are other methods with a recognised reputation in HCI for analysing
273 qualitative data, such as Content Analysis [31] or Thematic Analysis [32]. We
274 selected GT because this methodology allows us to construct theories, con-
275 cepts, hypotheses and propositions starting directly from the data and not
276 from the *a priori* assumptions, from other investigations, or existing theo-
277 retical frameworks.

Figure 4: The different phases of applying Grounded Theory over qualitative data coming from all three experimental conditions.

278 The purpose of the GT’s Open Coding phase after transcribing the qual-
279 itative data is to identify entities, to group them into categories, and to de-
280 scribe relevant properties and dimensions pertaining to a category. The codes
281 are extracted iteratively from the data in the process of analysis. Then, Axial
282 Coding identifies relationships between initial categories as well as conditions,
283 context variables, and resulting consequences. Finally, Selective Coding fo-
284 cuses on deliberately setting a focus on the analysis. Thus, core-category is
285 selected. As suggested by Armstrong et al. [33], inter-rater reliability of the
286 extraction of the codes and grouping them into categories was assessed by
287 two researchers along the whole process of the GT analysis.

288 In the Open coding phase, 132 unitary codes were extracted. Attributes
289 such as frequency, target, intensity or duration were annotated together with
290 each of the emerging codes (some samples of the codes extraction can be
291 observed in Table BB.3 in Appendix B of this paper.) These samples provide
292 an example of the quotes and the codification process we carried on.

293 Following the constant comparative method [28], a saturation of codes
294 and categories were reached in the Axial phase, according to the two re-

295 searchers. At this stage, five categories emerged from the initial codes: 1)
 296 interaction, 2) mediator—emotion, 3) attachment—confidence, 4) context,
 297 and 5) behaviour. As an example, Table 2 shows the codes from the people
 298 who interacted with the IoT-based persuasive appliance that emerged during
 299 the Open and Axial phases as well as the thematic categories in which these
 300 were grouped.

Table 2: Set of unitary codes along their axial categories extracted from people who interacted with the IoT-based persuasive coffee-maker.

Interaction	Attachment / Confidence	Mediator / Emotion	Context	Behaviour
Automation	Similarity	Group Awareness	Extrapolate behaviour	Acceptance
Satisfaction	Adherence	Generate discussion	Export to other devices	Adaptation
Understandable	Pleasure	Elicits Interest	Hawthorne effect	Pro-environmental self-perception
Comfort elicits awareness	Trust	Group inefficiency(-)	Private vs. Public setting	Aware of B. change
Comfort elicits efficiency	Dependency(-)	Media equation	Patterns	Group awareness
Comfort elicits inefficiency(-)	Disregard(-)	Proudness	Mirror effect	Comfort elicits awareness
Misunderstanding(-)	Expandable behaviour		Social-proof	Sense of control elicits efficiency
Disgruntlement(-)	Non-expandable B.(-)		Behaviour at home	Comfort elicits inefficiency(-)
Subject-expectancy effect(-)	Preservation			Consistency(-)
Efficacy vs. Efficiency	Proudness			Dependency(-)
Efficacy	Acceptance			Durability
Aesthetics	Transparency			Efficacy vs. Efficiency
Inefficiency(-)				Incomprehension(-)
Intelligent system				Learned helplessness(-)
Playfulness				Group inefficiency(-)
Data to take decisions(-)				Scale Consumption
Need of insightful data(-)				Low durability(-)
Different HCI model(-)				Obsolescence
Personal vs Group data				Patterns
Tailoring				Tailoring
Nudges				Unaware of behaviour change(-)
Useful				

301 Finally, the purpose of the Selective coding phase is to define the central
 302 category as the catalyst for the thematic categories. We elucidated that the
 303 central theme of the theory was the relationship between the people (employ-
 304 ees) and the augmented IoT-based appliance to cope with energy inefficiency
 305 jointly. This central theme encompasses the other five axial categories, as
 306 can be observed in the diagram of Figure 5.

Figure 5: The emerging theory obtained by analysing the qualitative data coming from all three experimental conditions through Grounded Theory.

307 According to Charmaz [28], the diagram is devised to organise the nascent
 308 theory and to see the relative power, scope, and direction of the categories
 309 in the analysis as well as the connections among them for linear narrative
 310 purposes. Therefore, the diagram should not be understood as a predictive
 311 or causal model that is mandatory to be followed to succeed in creating new
 312 IoT systems. What the incipient theory aims to bring attention is that for
 313 'Behaviour' change to occur (final theme) by means of 'Interacting' with
 314 IoT objects (initial theme), categories such as (Mediator—Emotion), (At-
 315 tachment—Confidence) and Use-context shall be taken into account when
 316 designing IoT-based persuasive systems. Thus, IoT augmented Things in
 317 the workplace context should provoke certain emotions to users, mediate be-
 318 tween conversations among human beings, create a sense of attachment to
 319 them, and generate confidence to bring pro-environmental awareness or ef-
 320 fectively change the behaviour. Furthermore, not all the paths interlinking
 321 the categories have to be pierced. In fact, those connections between themes
 322 that we considered non-compulsory have been depicted with a dashed lines⁵.

⁵We considered Emotion—Mediator and Confidence—Attachment as non-compulsory themes because we were unable to guarantee according to our analysis whether these

323 4. User Perception-based Design Hypotheses

324 As mentioned before, we applied the GT to the data obtained from groups
325 who interacted with the coffee-makers augmented with IoT-based persuasive
326 systems to extract design-insights that help to inform the design for similar
327 everyday intelligent devices in the future. Several quotes for all the conditions
328 were gathered. Still, for this paper, only relevant quotes from participants
329 that interacted with the persuasive IoT-based coffee maker are reported in
330 this section regarding each of the five/seven emerging themes. These quotes
331 are jointly offered with a discussion over the implications that the themes
332 have for the design of augmented objects that promote sustainable behaviour,
333 offering design-hypotheses in order to facilitate the implementation of the
334 exposed ideas for future designs.

335 4.1. Interaction

336 This category covered one of the most recurrent topics in the focus group
337 sessions, and it captured the majority of unitary codes in the GT analysis, as
338 can be observed in the first column of Table 2. Notably, we received positive
339 and pleasant feedback when participants evaluated the interaction with the
340 Interactive coffee maker. *"What did serve us well, were the red LEDs on the*
341 *periphery of the coffee-maker to make us to the idea of how we were going"* or
342 *"I think the visual feedback from the device has also given us clues as to how to*
343 *go about doing it."* In the referred table, the reader can also observe negative
344 symbols between brackets when feedback was considered unfavourable. For
345 instance, *"there were times when it turned red too quickly ... we think it*
346 *turns red very fast for the coffee we drink ... that will be 4-6 coffees a day ...*
347 *and then it is red"*. However, constructive criticism to improve the proposed
348 design was provided by some people, P1: *"I lacked some audible eco-feedback*
349 *when I put my mug on the appliance. Something like the NFC/RFID-based*
350 *readers that one can find in the turnstile of the Metro stations that give*
351 *you feedback about your pass checking"*. Surprisingly, some participants that
352 interacted with the persuasive IoT appliance missed some of the aspects that
353 were implemented in other experimental treatments, P2: *"I would like to*

themes that shared unitary codes could be merged or separated in sole categories as Interaction, Use-context or Behaviour. Further qualitative investigation through constant comparison and theoretical sampling (methods proposed by Glasser and Strauss [34]) should be carried out to decide on the unification or separation of these emerging themes.

354 *have a Web-dashboard where I could track my kWh*". The overall conclusion
355 of this category is that people felt satisfied with the feedback received because
356 it was intuitive and helpful to behave in an energy-efficient fashion.

357 **Design-hypothesis:** According to the conclusions extracted in the pre-
358 vious paragraph, and with our own experience in this experiment, to improve
359 the intuitiveness in the different users, the designers should be aware that
360 the 'one-size fits all' approach will not cover all user needs. As an example,
361 the persuasive IoT-based coffee-maker was the most efficient according to the
362 quantitative data. However, the users missed features of other treatments
363 with lower or none effectiveness (Quintal et al. [19] also reported a similar
364 situation. After receiving ambient visual cues to promote energy awareness,
365 participants in their study missed other extra features such as using histor-
366 ical data, social comparisons, presenting the impact on the environment or
367 the energy origin). Such finding let us understand that it is impossible to
368 please everyone with one design even when it seems to be just right for the
369 envisaged purpose.

370 Further, in the qualitative phase, it is more than probable that some of
371 the interviewees will miss features that the literature reckons that do not
372 work for changing the intended behaviour in the mid and long term (e.g.
373 provide kWh without comparisons, or provide financial incentives). These
374 opinions should be taken with extra care in the design phase because they
375 may blur the goal of changing the behaviour. We argue that this design-
376 insight is comparable to other contexts of HCI beyond IoT. Still, we consider
377 that a designer should be firm with the interactive proposal if it has been
378 validated through appropriate design methodologies.

379 *4.2. Mediator/Emotion*

380 Whereas the majority of the feedback provided about the interaction was
381 positive, the proposed persuasive design provoked polarised emotions that
382 were voiced in the focus group sessions. For example, P3 stated: "*Despite*
383 *the suggestions of the augmented appliance to leave it on, I felt cross leaving*
384 *the coffee maker switched on after preparing a coffee*". The opinions of P4
385 were more positive: "*I loved to know that we have a smart appliance in*
386 *the office*" or P5: "*It is funny to have one (the appliance)... for me, it is*
387 *like it was another member of the department*". This latter quote resounds
388 to the 'Media Equation Theory' that states that media and computers are
389 sometimes treated by people as if they were real humans [35]. Moreover,
390 P5's comment and that of P6: "*The coffee-maker sparked conversations about*

391 *energy consumption among colleagues. Overall during the initial weeks of the*
392 *set-up” correlated with the idea that augmented smart objects may have the*
393 *role of mediators to bring about reflections and conversations centred in the*
394 *topic that the designer wants to change.*

395 **Design-hypothesis:** We want to emphasise the idea that augmented
396 objects seem to be more than mere relays of eco-feedback, and they should be
397 conceived as new interactive actors in these situated environments. This idea
398 is not new in IoT [36] and was thoroughly investigated by Nass et al. [37] when
399 personal computers started to be widespread. In the case of the persuasive
400 coffee maker, sometimes office employees considered the device as a new
401 ally to cope with energy inefficiency, and they responded to smart object
402 personalities as the same way they responded to human personalities. The
403 peculiarity of these new actors is that they can cause mixed emotions to
404 users. These emotions are important because they are predictive factors for
405 technology adoption and technology appropriation.

406 4.3. Attachment/Confidence

407 As well as the previous category, again, two themes were brought together
408 by participants, and therefore they are presented into a single category. On
409 the one side, attachment to the smart persuasive appliance was found on sev-
410 eral participants that were upset when we communicated to them that the
411 smart devices were about to be removed, P7: *”I will miss the appliance. I*
412 *changed my perception of it...from being a bare device to consider it as some-*
413 *thing that is doing well for the environment”*. On the other side, confidence
414 in the technology was a recurrent theme because of the long time that people
415 shared with the device daily (one year), P8: *”I will always heed the eco-coffee*
416 *machine’s advice without any doubts...whenever it says ‘leave me on’, I leave*
417 *it on without thinking twice”*.

418 **Design-hypothesis:** We acknowledge that to strengthen these two themes,
419 the augmented everyday objects should be designed to remain close to the
420 people to keep the positive influence on the users throughout time. For that,
421 it is important to provide dynamic feedback that maintains the engagement
422 (this finding is in line with the critical review about persuasion and eco-
423 feedback pursued by Hermsen et al. [18] which was partially addressed by
424 Ching-Hu Lu [38] in the context of contextual adaptive IoT systems). More-
425 over, the information provided by the IoT objects have to be clear and trans-
426 parent and efforts should be put on making the IoT objects to become a
427 relevant authority in the field of application (in this case, many users trusted

428 in the coffee-maker information. Thus, Cialdini’s authority principle of per-
429 suasion played a leading role in this case [20]).

430 4.4. Use Context

431 The context of use is defined as ”the actual conditions under which a given
432 artifact is used in a normal working situation”. According to Pierce et al.
433 [39], there are two important dimensions when designing eco-feedback tech-
434 nologies for use-contexts: dweller control and third-party control. The work-
435 place lays into ”low dweller control, high third-party control”. Surprisingly
436 enough, the comments from experiment participants were not only related to
437 the place they work, and therefore, where they use the coffee machine daily.
438 Instead, the majority of opinions pointed out that some behaviours that one
439 does or learn in one use-context (e.g. at work) and export them to another,
440 maybe different, use-context (e.g. home settings - ”high dweller control, low
441 third-party control”). For example, P9 stated: *”Because here [at the work-
442 place] I switch off the coffee-maker, when I’m at home I pay more attention
443 to energy efficiency”*. However, care must be taken when designing objects
444 to form new behaviours in a specific context, P10: *”Sometimes at home, I
445 forget the coffee maker switched on because at work I’m used to leaving it on
446 since it (the augmented appliance) beg to me to do so”*.

447 **Design-hypothesis:** the IoT designers of persuasive everyday things
448 should take into account the spillover effects [40]. The spillover effect pro-
449 poses that engaging in one behaviour affects the probability of engagement or
450 disengaging in a second behaviour (consciously or unconsciously). Therefore,
451 the formed behaviours may be beneficial at one use-context (in our case in
452 the workplace) but are offering detrimental consequences in other contexts
453 (e.g. at home when no intelligent devices are there to remind the user to
454 do sustainable actions). Hence, they should be designed with the context in
455 mind and take into account all the consequences that may appear in on-the-
456 wild fields. For that, we suggest using unconventional probe tools [41] or
457 diary studies [42] in the design phase.

458 4.5. Behaviour

459 According to the last column of Table 2, this category, along with that
460 of interaction, was the most popular topic in the conversations that aroused
461 in the focus group sessions. The participants that interacted with the Per-
462 suasive condition were found to be the most aware individuals of the energy
463 inefficiency issue at the workplace, which was in line with the quantitative

464 data presented. Moreover, the comments from participants offered initial
465 hints of behaviour change, P11: *"We were fully aware of our misleading be-*
466 *haviour at the beginning of the experiment because the coffee maker turned red*
467 *due to excessive energy consumption"* or P12, *"The coffee maker has made*
468 *me aware of energy consumption. Now...sometimes after preparing a coffee,*
469 *I take two steps back to double-check if I've left the appliance on or off"*. The
470 voices from participants that assured that the newly formed behaviour will
471 remain throughout the time were the most relevant finding, P13: *"Somehow*
472 *I have started forming a habit...even if it is something unconscious"* or P14:
473 *"At the end, we all have got used to switching off the appliance. I believe*
474 *that we will maintain this easy course of actions"*.

475 **Design-hypothesis:**, one of the main problems that designers of IoT
476 for pro-environmental behaviour may find in successful studies (such as the
477 one reported here in terms of energy-reduced), is to witness a relapse effect
478 when the researcher completely removes the experimental conditions. The
479 same might occur even when participants diminish the use of the ICT-based
480 intervention after the novelty effect disappear. Such design-insight is pretty
481 much in line with Pereira et al. [43] or Peschiera et al. [44] who reported
482 evidence on response-relapse patterns on studies related to eco-feedback and
483 energy awareness interventions. Thus, the question we raise is: What would
484 be the contingency plan if there were no hints or advice to facilitate the
485 decision-making anymore? Or, if the rewards finished suddenly? Or, if the
486 gamification process became annoying to participants because of its repeti-
487 tiveness? Etc. The designer of augmented everyday objects should carefully
488 plan the longitudinal extent of his/her system and reflect upon foreseeable
489 consequences of feedback removal. A proposal would be to taper the feedback
490 off during intervals instead of doing it abruptly or creating context-aware
491 gradually adaptive systems based on the most up-to-date user status (this
492 latter approach was studied experimentally in a controlled environment by
493 Ching-Hu Lu [38]).

494 5. Applying Emerging Guidelines on a New IoT Device

495 Each of the categories derived from the analyses represent a thematic
496 design-hypothesis, enabling researchers to build effective interventions in the
497 workplace that place in the centre the relationship between people and the
498 augmented device to reduce energy waste: from how people will interact
499 with the device, through the emotions which the device may arise, the con-

500 conversations that the device itself might foster among users, the confident or
501 attachment to the suggestions provided by the intelligent device, the envi-
502 ronment or context where the device will be used, and finally, the behaviour
503 to be promoted. With this conceptual framework, in the following, we im-
504 plement each of the design-hypothesis on a new everyday IoT object that
505 aims at improving the energy efficiency of equipment in workstations in an
506 office-based work environment. Firstly, ideation and development of the pro-
507 totype are introduced to contextualise the theoretical implementation. Then,
508 the emerging theory is applied in the context of the presented device, linking
509 each of the five emerging themes with the different design features and design
510 decisions.

511 *5.1. The Interactive Coaster*

512 To deepen in the research and understand the practical issues that emerged
513 in the theoretical approach, an interactive IoT prototype was developed. The
514 Interactive Coaster (IC) is a device intended to help the users become more
515 aware of the energy that they use through the electronic devices that sur-
516 round them in their workspace (e.g. a computer, monitor or the mobile
517 phone charger). The IC supports the user in the daily routine at work by
518 periodically showing visual information about their energy consumption level
519 and also serves to its primary function (i.e. act as a coaster for placing on
520 top of it a coffee mug or a bottle of water). Besides, it also provides alerts
521 to use the devices more efficiently (e.g. to turn off the screen when it is not
522 used (during breaks), foster the usage of the sleep mode, or switch off the
523 computer when leaving the workplace during longer periods). To do so, the
524 IC is connected to a smart plug that collects the energy consumption of the
525 whole workstation. The IC (which can be observed in Figure 6), is a rounded
526 coaster made of wood and includes concentric methacrylate circles that cast
527 light through RGB LEDs. A coaster was selected among other design ideas
528 due to its high visibility in the desktop environment. Besides, it is always
529 visible and can be used by everyone at any moment. To improve the ef-
530 fectiveness of the feedback provided, the diameter of the coaster is slightly
531 higher than an average mug or glass. In this way, the individual can (almost)
532 always observe the outer light-ring, although a recipient is on top of it.

Figure 6: The IC showing some of the states that can display.

533 The lights of the coaster show a different colour depending on the average
 534 energy expenditure. Green is used to inform that the energy consumption is
 535 low; yellow to report that the waste is raising; orange to alert that the user
 536 is close to its average consumption and red when energy usage has overtaken
 537 the average consumption of previous days. The IC features different modes
 538 and visualisations to enhance user awareness and motivation about energy
 539 efficiency. 1) A historical energy consumption visualisation (when the user
 540 pushes the central button of the IC the four different circles of the coaster
 541 show a different colour depending on the energy expenditure of each time
 542 unit - previous day, current week, current month, current year); 2) an au-
 543 tomatic visualisation alerts about the energy consumption consumed during
 544 the workday; 3) a vibration alarm buzzes when different energy expenditure
 545 levels are exceeded (the colour coding remains the same as current consump-
 546 tion or historical information); 4) "party mode" lights a visualisation with
 547 random colour coding, aiming at offering playful value through colourful and
 548 animated visual effects; and 5) a "snooze mode" is activated when the user
 549 flips over the Interactive Coaster switching off all the lights until it is flipped
 550 over again. The IC is able to connect to the Internet extracting all the infor-
 551 mation about energy consumption through a Wi-Fi module built-in in the
 552 System on Chip (SoC), which controls the whole operation of the IoT device.

553 The coaster has been designed following a user-centric approach, and its
 554 design was addressed in a previous work of the authors[45]. A summary of
 555 the steps followed to design the IC from scratch were: 1) the first ideation
 556 process, where the goal was to establish an initial approach to generate new
 557 ideas, prototypes or mock-ups based on the users' needs; 2) the development
 558 of a Low-Fi prototype of the IC. This early version was intended to provide
 559 an initial approach of the physical design of the coaster, the information
 560 that it would provide, and the main interactions that should be implemented

561 on it; 3) user research with the device, where we sought to share the first
562 design ideas with them to understand their insights; and 4) the refinement
563 of the prototype, implementing the design with the ideas emerged from the
564 qualitative study. During the design process (third phase), we involved seven
565 end-users following a semi-structured interview approach after letting them
566 interact with the early versions of the IC. Expressly, the interviewees were
567 initially provided with free time (2-5 minutes) to interact with the device,
568 and then, the two researchers started asking questions. We asked them about
569 their opinion of the IC, which metrics were preferred to understand their
570 energy consumption, the colour-coding preferred, which kind of feedback was
571 more understandable for them, where they would place the coaster within
572 their workstation, etc. With this information and the qualitative insights
573 from the GT approach, we finalised the design of the new IoT object. In the
574 following section, we shed light on how the nascent theory and its design-
575 hypotheses were implemented in the IC.

576 *5.2. Implementing the emerging theory on the IC*

577 The central idea extracted from the results of the Grounded Theory anal-
578 ysis sets the basis of the incipient theory about the relationship between the
579 augmented IoT device and people to reduce energy waste. The five/seven
580 design-hypotheses of the emerging themes (interaction, mediator/emotion,
581 attachment/confidence, use context, and behaviour) are used as drivers to
582 face the design phase in the ideation and development of the IC.

583 *5.2.1. Interaction*

584 The interaction was one of the most relevant topics in the evaluation ses-
585 sions. Therefore, it should be a key driver to improve the relationship with
586 the device. To facilitate the understanding of the "Interaction" term and to
587 avoid comprehension issues, we consider it necessary to clarify the approach
588 of the terminology used in this work. In this context, interaction is under-
589 stood as the actions and relations between an individual and an interface.
590 To go in-depth through this generic conception of the term, the approach
591 proposed by Diefenbach [46] is used, where the Interaction term is classified
592 through three different levels: 1) the Why level, the most general. This is re-
593 lated to the experience, emotions, and subjective impression when interacting
594 with something; 2) the What level, related to the functionality of any interac-
595 tion, and 3) the How level, related to concrete operations, motor-actions and
596 elementary attributes. Following the design-hypothesis from the Interaction

597 theme (i.e. "One size does not fit all" [47]) and the Diefenbach's rationale
598 explained above, we devised the IC through a user-centric approach, devel-
599 oping an iterative process of design and evaluation and involving the user in
600 the process. The heterogeneity of the individuals and their different needs,
601 emotions or perspectives were specially addressed in the evaluation sessions
602 to extract design features to implement in the IC. Hence, different features
603 were implemented, aiming at offering different and complementary strategies
604 to cover the needs of the existing different user stereotypes/segments. Thus,
605 automatic visualisation of energy expenditure, the historical visualisation of
606 the average consumption of different time units, and alarms or warnings when
607 certain expenditure is raised. These design strategies were developed taking
608 into account the research developed by Lockton et al. [48] and Petkov et al.
609 [49] where they offer specific design solutions addressed to the user diversity
610 based in the behavioural models of the human system ([48]) and the personal
611 norms, values and beliefs ([49]). In essence, in the IC different interactive
612 approaches were implemented, offering end-users a wide range of feedback to
613 address the diversity of needs (e.g. messages with different cognitive load,
614 context-feedback in time through the warnings, delayed feedback through
615 automatic visualisation and feedback on-demand through historical energy
616 consumption). We can not ensure that with this, we have covered all user
617 needs, but we believe that this approach will reduce the end-user expecta-
618 tions considerably on missed features. Further explanation about how the
619 IC addresses the user diversity can be found here [45].

620 5.2.2. *Emotion/Mediator*

621 The emotions were another factor that emerged from the relationship
622 between the device and the individuals. As the qualitative results showed,
623 feelings and emotional bonding are inherent to the relationship with the
624 device, and thus they must be taken into account when designing interactive
625 smart artifacts. The idea of the device as a mediator of conversations or
626 interactions around energy efficiency is also linked with the feelings derived
627 from this emotional bond. That is, if the values offered by the device resonate
628 with the emotional needs of the user, the device can act as a mediator not
629 only to conversations but also for the behaviour that the device aims to
630 change.

631 The IC implements the emotional factors through product design. The
632 top side of the IC has been designed taking into account the idea of the tree
633 trunk and its rings. This strategy offers a visual metaphor that is intended

634 to impact the emotional side of the individual. In order to strengthen this
635 metaphor, the material selected for the case was wood. Besides, the visual
636 design of the RGB lights and the appealing party mode are features intended
637 to enhance the emotional properties of the device through design patterns.

638 The mediator theme was also implemented on the IC through its intended
639 placement on the workstation to foster high visibility of the device
640 at any moment by its owner and close colleagues and peers. Furthermore,
641 we implemented a colour-coding that resonates with the traffic-light analogy.
642 This corresponds to an emotional codification based on the work proposed
643 by Valdez and Gao [50, 51].

644 5.2.3. Attachment/Confidence

645 Attachment and confidence are abstract and complex factors closely re-
646 lated to the relationship between the device and the individuals. Therefore,
647 special care must be put when addressing these concepts to avoid strategies
648 that may cause a negative effect on them. A variety of strategies can be
649 followed to improve the level of attachment of the user towards the IC and
650 gain confidence in the long term. Taking into account the design-hypotheses,
651 the device should be located close to the user or, at least, in his/her field of
652 view (whilst being careful not to create continuous attention theft). In this
653 regard, the device has been designed to be small and easy to be moved to
654 one place or another within the workstation in order to not be obtrusive to
655 employees (See Figure 7).

Figure 7: People at workplace placing the IC on different locations of their desktop.

656 The confident theme is implemented by offering consistency over the vi-
 657 sual information provided and openness. On the one side, we explain to
 658 the users that what they observe with colours in the IC is an analogy of
 659 the real energy consumption being monitored by a smart plug connected to
 660 their workstation. To provide adaptive feedback as suggested by Hermsen et
 661 al. [18], the IC calculates the maximum target consumption for each day pro-
 662 viding different colour-based interactions depending on how close the user is
 663 to exceed the calculated target. On the other side, we offer them the option
 664 of visualising the energy consumed in a digital time-series graph to corrob-
 665 orate that the visual cues built-in the device correspond to the power being
 666 drawn (see Figure 8).

Figure 8: An example of one of the Web-based graphs. Users are able to select the time interval and the energy data frequency (15mins, 1h, 1day) of their associated smart plug. In this example, the user has selected observe its consumption in a daily-basis.

667 5.2.4. Use Context

668 The Interactive Coaster is intended to promote energy efficiency in an
 669 office-based work environment and therefore, the limitation of this narrow
 670 context should be taken into account. To minimise the potential negative
 671 spillover effects related to a cause-effect design (e.g. forgot to switch off
 672 the monitor at home because the user does not have a blinking coaster in
 673 its private setting), the IC is designed to provide overall awareness about
 674 energy-efficiency. Although the device is not designed to send alerts at spe-
 675 cific moments (e.g. vibrate if the user is about to go home in order to recall
 676 him/her to switch everything off), it is possible for users to learn how the
 677 IC works and to see the existing causal relationships between their every-

678 day actions and work patterns and the different colours that the IC shows.
679 Through the everyday visualisation, the users are invited to reflect on their
680 behaviour and energy expenditure rather than expect triggers and alerts from
681 the coaster at specific moments during the day. Therefore, the IC's objective
682 is to enhance overall awareness and eventually energy savings rather than
683 recall a specific undesired action continuously. We believe that this design is
684 prone to provide positive spillover effects in other contexts.

685 *5.2.5. Behaviour*

686 The Interactive Coaster has been primarily designed to enhance aware-
687 ness and to serve as an energy ally to the user. Although the promotion of
688 the pro-environmental behaviour is the objective, the implications of the use
689 context place the performance of the action as a consequence of the awareness
690 generated by the eco-feedback (this is in line with Azjen's Theory of Planned
691 Behaviour where intentions are the pivotal determinant for behaviour to oc-
692 cur [52]). Therefore, and taking into account, the design-hypothesis of this
693 theme, the potential relapse effect derived from the elimination of the tech-
694 nology at the end of the experimental phase should be less unfavourable.
695 Besides, the own energy usage patterns learned by users after having inter-
696 acted with the coaster for a short period could drive to more sustainable
697 actions. Moreover, these might be more likely to stick because the behaviour
698 change is not linked to the device but to the motivation and new energy-
699 related knowledge of the individual.

700 **6. Conclusions**

701 In this article, the qualitative data derived from a set of focus groups after
702 carrying out a longitudinal experiment on energy awareness at the workplace
703 were analysed using the Grounded Theory approach. GT analysis was ap-
704 plied to produce new insights into the design process of novel persuasive phys-
705 ical interfaces or augmented everyday objects that promote energy-efficient
706 behaviour change that sticks throughout the time at the workplace. The
707 emerging theory presents five categories: 1) interaction, mediator/emotion,
708 3) attachment/confidence, 4) context, and 5) behaviour. Each of these cat-
709 egories derived from the analyses represents a thematic design-insight, en-
710 abling researchers to build effective interventions in the workplace that place
711 in the centre the relationship between people and the augmented device to

712 reduce energy waste (the central category of the emerging theory). In a lin-
713 ear fashion the emerging theory shed light on how design IoT devices taking
714 into account the interactions that users will have with them, through the
715 emotions which the device may arise, the conversations that the device itself
716 might foster among users, the environment or context where the device will
717 be installed and used, and finally, the behaviour to be promoted. To gather
718 more data and deepening on this research line, a new interactive IoT device
719 (a coaster) was developed by implementing one by one each of the themes
720 extracted from the user perception-based theory. The difficulties of address-
721 ing the mapping from theory to design have been pointed out throughout
722 the article. We deem that the endeavour of designing a new device within
723 the premises of the theory has enriched the framework substantially since we
724 demonstrated that it can be applied on a real interactive design. As a future
725 line of work, the evaluation of the effectiveness of the new IoT device will
726 provide new arguments and enhancements over the validity of the themes.
727 We expect designers, engineers, makers or even hobbyists in the intersec-
728 tion between technology-enablers (through IoT) and behavioural scientists
729 to benefit from the presented work.

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898 **Appendix A. Offices and Bussines Description**

899 **Bailen:** It is a coworking space in an old building in Bilbao where archi-
900 tects, urban planners, designers, and multimedia producers coexist. All the
901 people who work in this space are in a room with shared tables, leaving the
902 coffee area in a separate room. In addition to the coffee machine, there are
903 other appliances: microwave, dishwasher and water heater for tea. In this
904 type of space, it is easy to forget a device switched on and be in this state
905 unnoticed during all the time in which the room is unoccupied.

906 **Comunica:** It is an administrative office within a university in Bilbao.
907 Each of the people who work there develops management or communication
908 functions and therefore has a personal desk. The coffee machine is hidden
909 in a cupboard and every time they want to use it they have to carry out the
910 following process: open the cupboard, turn on the coffee machine, put the
911 capsule, make the coffee, remove the capsule, the cup and leave everything
912 clean, for last, close the closet again. Being so specific and conscious of the
913 process of preparing a coffee, it is difficult for people in this space to leave
914 the appliance on. The reason for having the coffee machine hidden is because
915 it is a space where many outsiders get in and employees do not want to have
916 the device in view to visitors.

917 **Computing, Life, Mobility, and MORElab:** The four groups do
918 research in computer science and belong to a research center attached to a
919 university in Bilbao. The four groups are arranged in separate places within
920 a clear space of 2000m2. Being such a large place, there is no interaction
921 between the groups or visual contact as the researchers develop their func-
922 tions in semi-isolated cubicles. As they are different groups, each of them
923 has a coffee machine for personal use that is located in one of the free tables
924 corresponding to their work units. In each group, there are members who
925 have visual contact with the coffee maker and others who do not. As a par-
926 ticularity, it should be taken into account that the members of the Mobility
927 group usually coincide when it comes to making the coffee break, while in
928 the other groups, each person usually prepares the coffee individually. Some
929 of the groups have a microwave and refrigerator.

930 **ServGen:** It is a workspace that serves as the secretariat of a research
931 center attached to a university in Bilbao. In this space, there are several
932 offices for private use and common rooms where administrative staff works.
933 The coffee machine is placed in one of these spaces. Only one of the workers
934 has direct visual contact with the device.

935 **IEEC:** It is a research group related to computer science and education
936 belonging to a university in Madrid where its members are divided into 2
937 separate offices. Their coffee machine is located inside a working labora-
938 tory along with other mechanical machines such as drills and lathes. This
939 laboratory is separated from the two offices, therefore there is no visual con-
940 tact with the appliance. Hence, it is easy to leave it switched off due to
941 absentmindedness.

942 **Techabout:** It is a cabin located in a business incubator of technology-
943 based companies in Bilbao. Being a small room does not have separate spaces
944 and therefore the coffee machine is on top of a piece of furniture in the center
945 of the room. Each of the people who work there has their own table and they
946 all have visual contact with the coffee machine.

947 **Tecnologica:** It is a technological company in Madrid with a diaphanous
948 space of about 1500m² where the workers are grouped in round tables orga-
949 nized by ongoing projects. The space of the coffee machine is separated into
950 an adjoining room that is a full kitchen. In addition to all the appliances that
951 can be found in a conventional kitchen, this space has vending machines. In
952 that place, people can eat or relax because there are tables, sofas, and access
953 to the outside. There are many people in the company who usually have
954 coffee together at the same time.

955 **Appendix B. Transformation from Quotes to Codes in GT**

Table B.3: Three samples of the Open coding phase: From the quote, to the intermediate action to the final codes.

Quote	Intermediate Action	Unitary Codes
I have continued to use the coffee maker as I did before and it has not meant any change to how I have used it or even thought about it	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Showing comfort and transparency about the research Ensuring that he/she has not changed the way the coffee maker is used 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Transparent measurement. Consistency No change in conscious habit
To me personally, it has not made me more efficient / conscious with other energy consumption devices	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * Ensuring that you have not changed efficiency habits Showing security when it comes to saying that you have not extrapolated the habit to other devices There is no self-perception of behavior change with other electrical appliances. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> * do not extrapolate change of non-conscious habit
but now, having the visual stimuli there. Even though there are times we say: "why is it red if we have not done anything" ... then having it invites you ... to say ... uh I'm going to turn it off.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Attributing to the interaction of the coffee maker the improvement in the efficiency of the group Showing contrariety to interaction at certain times 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> useful interaction initial disappointment adaptation